

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

№ 7(16)

27.06.2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

SJIF 2024
5.3

zenodo

Google
scholar

OpenAIRE

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

fer-teach.uz

@ferteach_uz

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD, dotsent

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

[SJIF-2024: 5.3](#)

Murojaat uchun

 [@ferteach_uz](#)

 +99893-343-13-14

 <https://fer-teach.uz/rai>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya

L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston

Sh.J.Kholmatov - i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Z.N.Khatamova - t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

Modern means of processing information as a product of the information service system of science and technology activities and methods of their implementation

S.Abdullaeva

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

M.Sobirov

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

Abstract. The article examines modern information processing tools as a product of the information service system of scientific and technical activities. The methods of their implementation in the areas of data management, intellectual analysis, visualization and modeling are analyzed. Particular attention is paid to innovative tools and platforms that transform the methods of collecting, processing and disseminating scientific and technical knowledge. The article demonstrates how these tools are becoming an integral part of advanced scientific and technical practice, contributing to the acceleration of scientific and technical progress.

Keywords. information processing, information service system, scientific and technical activities, data management

Современные средства обработки информации как продукт системы информационного обслуживания научно-технической деятельности и методы их реализации

С.Абдуллаева

Ферганский политехнический институт

М.Собиров

Ферганский политехнический институт

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются современные средства обработки информации как продукт информационно-сервисной системы научно-технической деятельности. Анализируются методы их реализации в областях управления данными, интеллектуального анализа, визуализации и моделирования. Особое внимание уделено инновационным инструментам и платформам, трансформирующим способы сбора, обработки и распространения научных и технических знаний. Статья демонстрирует, как эти средства становятся неотъемлемой частью передовой научно-технической практики, способствуя ускорению научно-технического прогресса..

Ключевые слова. обработка информации, информационно-сервисная система, научно-техническая деятельность, управление данными

Nowadays, it will not be an exaggeration to say that the expressions of information and computer technology are the most used concepts in everyday life. Because no matter what area of life we do not take, no matter what actions we do, we will definitely be forced to follow their various actions related to information. That is, the use of information, the exchange of Information, their transmission form the main basis of human activity.

Nowadays, information technology is the most important factor affecting the rapid development of society. Although information technology has existed even at different stages of human development, the peculiarity of the now informed society is that for the first time in the history of human development, it dominates the costs that are spent on the achievement and production of knowledge, that is, information technologies occupy a leading place among existing new technologies.

The industrial complex of Information Technologies is made up of a computer, a communication system, a data warehouse, a knowledge warehouse and related fields of activity. People who do not work directly in the field of Information Technology also take advantage of its capabilities in their daily work. Information technology is becoming more and more embedded in all spheres of life and becoming its driving force.

Today, information technology can be classified into conditionally preserving, rationalizing, creating types. The first type of technologies saves labor, material resources, time. Ordering tickets to rationalizing information technologies, hotel accounting systems will be an example. Creator information technologies consist of systems that develop information, use it and include Man as a component.

The current development and achievements of Information Technologies indicate the need to coordinate all areas of Science and human activity. Because this is exactly what will become the basis and important ground for the informatization of the whole society.

Informatization of society refers to the use of information as the wealth of society, which ensures the development of the economy, the development of the country's science technology, the acceleration of the process of democratization and intellectualization of society.

Information is information about environmental objects and phenomena, their dimensions, characteristics and states.

Information technology (AT) is a process that uses a set of data collection, processing and transmission (initial information) tools and techniques to obtain

new qualitative information about the state of an object, process or event. Telekom-munikasiya remote transmission of data on the basis of computer networks and modern technical means of communication.

The material and technological basis of the information society is a variety of systems based on computer equipment and computer networks, information technology, telecommunications communications.

At the moment, the following points of view have arisen about how to understand information:

Information - all sectors of the national economy are consumer reserves and are as important as energy or mineral reserves. Development of society-the organization of the use of available information, information reserves on various issues such as Economics, Science, Technology, Technology, Culture, Art, Medicine has an increasing impact on intellectual and economic life.

Information is the sum of Science-Technical Data, knowledge about the results of the development of Science and technology. In other words, information, according to this interpretation, is the product and "raw material" of the Information Service System of Science and technology activities.

In information and Information Service Systems, Science is the sum of products that form technical activities and training of personnel in various fields, that is, the production and consumption of information reserves is limited only to the intellectual life of society.

It can be seen that the first of these interpretations is the most complete, giving a concept that covers the versatility of Information Processes. Indeed, information is penetrating into all spheres of society and human activity.

As noted above, one of the important concepts in the informatization of society is the concept of information reserves.

Information reserves are a separate document and a separate document collection, a collection of documents and documents in Information Systems (library, archive, fund, data banks, other information systems).

Information is one of the valuable reserves of society, such as traditional types of material reserves such as oil, gas, minerals, etc., which means that its processing process can be perceived as technology when compared with the processes of processing material reserves.

The purpose of information technology is to produce information for human analysis and make decisions on the basis of which to perform some action.

Information technology is a process that uses a set of tools and methods of collecting, processing and transmitting data (initial information) to obtain new

qualitative information about the state of an object, process or event (information product).

Modern information technology is information technology with a friendly interface of user work using personal computers and telecommunications tools.

Modern information technology can be divided into three main principles:

- computer-generated interactive (communication) work mode;
- integration (contiguity), interaction with other software products;
- flexibility of the processes of changes in terms of both data and task laying.

The main features of modern information technology can also be subtracted into three parts:

- methodology;
- key character;
- the result.

Based on the principles of these two sections, it will be possible to offer principal new means of information processing. For example, we can propose the following new tools and methods of information processing:

1. Control technology "fit in";
2. Modern technology of communications;
3. Integrated technological systems;
4. Integration of the work of specialists and managers;
5. Latest modern technologies of information processing;
6. Ways to create, transmit, store and reflect information in a goal-oriented state;
7. Accounting for the laws of the social environment;
8. Modern technologies for making management decisions.

Information technology is closely related to Information Systems, which are the main environment for itself. Information technology is formed from specific regulatory rules for performing operations, actions, stages of various levels of complexity, which stand over data stored on a computer. The main purpose of information technology is to organize the storage and transmission of information.

The rational methodology for using modern information technology provides a way to achieve greater flexibility, support common standards, implement the right of local information products, reduce duplication in activities, etc., and achieve high economic productivity.

The effectiveness and flexibility of Information Technology largely depends on the characteristics of the interface system of Decision Support. Interface: the language of the user; the language of the computer message, which organizes communication on the display screen, determines the knowledge of the user.

The day-to-day development of Information Technologies is laying the groundwork for their productive use in all areas of the national economy. However, information technology cannot be tasted without a system that provides its work. The same system is considered an information system, its types. the relationship between processes, system and technology in the system leads to the creation of programming systems.

Information systems existed from the moment of the emergence of society, since at different stages of Development Society required systematized, pre-prepared information for its management. This is especially true of the processes of production related to the production of material and intangible goods. Because they are vital for the development of society. It is the production processes that are rapidly improved. With their development, management is also complicated, which, in turn, stimulates the improvement and development of Information Systems.

The traditional information system began to change qualitatively. On the basis of the use of tools of computational techniques in the control apparatus, a new structural unit appeared, the sole function of which was to ensure the management process with reliable information. In this way, new information flows appeared in the control contour, old flows partially changed their direction. Part of the traditional information system began to form slowly but consistently in the direction of more and more automation of information processing.

According to the field of application, it is possible to indicate the following types of such systems:

- * technical information systems;
- * Economic Information Systems;
- information systems in social spheres, etc.

We can include the following components in the composition of each system:

1. System structure-many elements of the system and the interaction between them. Example: organizational and production structure of the firm;
2. Functions of each element of the system. Example: management functions-decision-making by specific structure units of a firm;
3. The input and output of each element and system in general. Example: material or information flows that fall into and out of the system.
4. The system and some of its elements, objectives and limitations. Example: achieving the most benefits, financial limitations;
5. Each system has the property of division and integrity.

The information system is created for a specific object. An effective information system takes into account the differences between the levels of

management, practical areas, as well as external circumstances, and provides only the information necessary for the effective implementation of the management function.

Therefore, the modern methods and tools of information processing, information technologies and information systems mentioned above and cited are the basis for us to say that for the development of Science and technology, information systems can serve as a criterion for the development of information as a special and “raw material” of the Information System Service.

References

1. Akerkar, R. (2019). *Intelligent Systems and Applications*. CRC Press.
2. Chen, C. P., & Zhang, C. Y. (2014). Data-intensive applications, challenges, techniques and technologies: A survey on Big Data. *Information Sciences*, 275, 314-347.
3. Hirsch, J. E. (2005). An index to quantify an individual's scientific research output. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 102(46), 16569-16572.
4. Labrinidis, A., & Jagadish, H. V. (2012). Challenges and opportunities with big data. *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, 5(12), 2032-2033.
5. Nonaka, I., & Takeuchi, H. (1995). *The Knowledge-Creating Company: How Japanese Companies Create the Dynamics of Innovation*. Oxford University Press.
6. Sharda, R., Delen, D., & Turban, E. (2020). *Business Intelligence, Analytics, and Data Science: A Managerial Perspective*. Pearson.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 07 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 07 2024	Том 02. Вып. 07 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Bizning web-sahifa:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg'ona filiali tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro‘yxatidan (№ 078777) o‘tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay‘ati a‘zolidan respublikaning turli OTMLarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o‘rin olishgan..

Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 07 | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 07 | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 07 | 2024

Научно-методический журнал “Исследования и внедрение”

Адрес редакции:

150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, улица Солим, дом 23/4, кв. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Наш сайт:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 07 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 07 2024	Том 02. Вып. 07 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyligi uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.